

Best Practice Approaches to Financing the Forestry Transition

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Context and Motivation

While afforestation supports several ecosystem services, existing market structures and government policies such as the Common Agriculture Policy have favoured agricultural land uses and afforestation rates have not increased in line with policy goals. To overcome this challenge, novel financial instruments and management mechanisms are needed to compensate for the opportunity cost of transitioning land from agriculture to forestry. This best practice guide summarises outcomes from an expert stakeholder analysis. The results of this study suggest that land-use stakeholders recognise the local and national environmental benefits of native afforestation, while also understanding the economic and financial challenges which currently hamper native forestry growth. These results identify a need for novel financial support to make the land-use transition to native forestry financially feasible and economically attractive to landowners over the long term.

Figure 1 Barriers to Afforestation. Best practice necessary to increase afforestation needs to address policy barriers as well as social barriers. Policy barriers comprised of a deterioration in levels of trust in government due to the poor prior history on long-term support for afforestation. Within the policy domain, excessive administration was linked to issues around identifying eligible land, as many wetlands and protected habitats were excluded from afforestation. This was compounded by a lengthy application process (2-3 years). Social barriers were identified as a second significant barriers as production efficiency and proactivity in land management were prioritised. Also, farmers who considered or undertook afforestation were viewed as making that land unavailable to other local landowners who would have valued its availability to increase their own productive capacity.

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Figure 2 Opportunities for Afforestation. Design principles to enhance existing afforestation programmes emerged from the third phase of the Delphi method. The discussion on opportunities for afforestation focused on localising forestry efforts using existing farmer networks and designing specific interventions based on local landscapes. Improved take-up of afforestation within this local context was expected to be realised through a focus on native afforestation and small-scale woodlands and/or agroforestry.

Key Takeaways

The opportunities for local forestry reside in the following design features:

- There is a need for longer term, multigenerational payments to farmer landowners for afforestation. The government can set the foundations for increased private sector involvement in financing afforestation. The private sector can allow for increased compensation to farmers, longer payment periods, and may reduce the bureaucratic burden of solely public programmes.
- Our analysis recommends local community scale programmes that can use more flexible strategies adapted to the needs of the individual landowners and the local area. Forestry benefits to individual farmers include longer grazing periods and nutrient control while local communities can benefit from improved water quality, flood control, and forestry recreational opportunities. To unlock these benefits, local communities, forestry cooperatives, and farmer networks need flexible, bottom-up solutions such as customised continuous cover forestry which would allow the species best suited to local conditions to be grown and harvested gradually, ensuring a steady flow of long-term income.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.